

REVIEW ARTICLE

**TOXICITY STUDIES ON VOLATILE OIL FROM DIFFERENT
MEDICINAL PLANT BY USING BRINE SHRIMP LETHALITY ASSAY****Nivedha V*¹, Ayeesha Lubaba M¹, Deepak Muthu S¹,
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Abstract:

Natural products, particularly plant-derived substances, have been key in drug discovery, offering solutions to prevent or treat various diseases. Phytochemicals, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenes, play vital roles in health by reducing cell damage, a leading cause of many health issues. The volatile oil contain bioactive compounds and offer numerous therapeutic benefits, including antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, spasmolytic, carminative, hepatoprotective, antiviral and essential oils showing promise against cancers. Recent studies suggest essential oils can enhance the effectiveness of chemotherapy drugs, reducing the necessary dosage. The chemical composition and cytotoxicity of essential oils from plants like *Moringa oleifera*, *Ceiba pentandra*, *thymus vulgaris*, *Ocimum gratissimum*, *Acalypha ornata* Hochst remain under explored, hindering their therapeutic application. Furthermore, The Brine Shrimp Lethality Test (BSLT) is commonly employed to evaluate the toxicity of various substances, including volatile oils. The BSLT offers a simple, cost-effective, and efficient method for assessing the toxic potential of these oils. In this assay, brine shrimp larvae (*Artemia salina*) are exposed to varying concentrations of the volatile oil, and the mortality rate is observed over a specified period. The results help in determining the lethal concentration of the oil and its potential risk to aquatic organisms. The BSLT is particularly valuable for studying the lethality of volatile oils with various chemical compositions, offering insights into their pharmacological properties and ecological safety.

Keyword: Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay, Volatile Oil, Lethality Concentration, Cytotoxicity

Abbreviations

BSLT-Brine shrimp lethality assay

EO- Essential oil

TLC - Thin Layer Chromatography

CC - Column Chromatography

GC- Gas Chromatography

HPLC - High Performance Liquid Chromatography

HPTLC - High Performance thin Layer Chromatography

Introduction:

Substances of natural products have been a source of inspiration in new drugs discovery, which are able to prevent or treat many diseases. It is fascinating that many of the medications we use today are derived from the extensive study of the chemical compositions and therapeutic effects of plants. Plants are recognized for their significant medicinal properties, thanks to the bioactive compounds they contain, known as phytochemicals. These plant-based chemicals play a crucial role in maintaining human health by reducing the risk of cellular damage, which is a leading cause of various health issues. Some examples include alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, phenolics, tannins, glycosides, terpenes, and others. Essential oils which are generally composed of terpenes, obtained from different plant organs by steam distillation or any suitable mechanical process without heating are also important natural products with a wide range of bioactivity¹.

Certain spices such as cloves, cinnamon, mustard, garlic, ginger, and mint have long been used as traditional remedies in India. In Egypt, essential oils have been extracted for over 3,000 years due to their significant value in various applications. The production of the essential oils dates back to more than 2000 years in the Far East, with early modern technologies taking place in Saudi Arabia in the 9th century².

Essential oils (EOs) are volatile substances obtained from the flowers, leaves, stems, roots, or fruits of aromatic plants by steam distillation. EOs, usually of complex composition are composed of secondary metabolites of plants³. At room temperature, the pure EOs from natural plants are volatile oily liquids, normally soluble in organic solvents and lipids. Essential oils are highly volatile and can rapidly evaporate upon exposure to air. To the naked eye, some EOs are colorless, while more common ones are yellow or orange (*Citri reticulatae pericarpium* oil and *lemon* oil)⁴; some are even indigo (*Matricaria chamomilla* oil) or green (*Artemisiae argyi folium* oil). Most EOs sits on top of water because they are less dense, such as citronella oil, lime oil, or orange oil, while there are some heavier than water, such as cinnamon oil, clove oil, or garlic oil. The first recorded use of EOs abroad was in ancient Egypt, India, and Persia⁵.

Many natural compounds isolated from plants have shown a broad spectrum of biological activities. Among these various kinds of natural compounds, essential oils possess promising biological activities and have been of potential sources of natural products. They have been studied for their benefits as alternative remedies for the treatment as well as preventive agents of many infectious diseases and are confirmed to have various pharmacological effects, such as spasmolytic, carminative,

hepatoprotective, antiviral and anticarcinogenic effects. The essential oils are extracted from aromatic and medicinal plants using several methods such as water or steam distillation, solvent extraction, expression under pressure, supercritical fluid and subcritical water extractions^{6,7}.

Previous study indicates that plant-derived essential oil possesses anti-tumor potential against leukemia as well as cancers of the mouth, breast, lung, prostate, liver, and colon. Research has shown that certain compounds in essential oils may enhance the cytotoxic effects of chemotherapy drugs, such as docetaxel, paclitaxel, and 5-fluorouracil, on various cancer cell line. This suggests that the dosage of these drugs may be reduced while still having the same effect⁸. To date, the cytotoxic and chemical properties of AEO derived from *A. sinensis* have not been extensively studied, which limits its potential use as a therapeutic agent or medication. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the chemical components of AEO through GC-MS analysis and assess its cytotoxic effects using brine shrimp (*Artemia salina*) and various cancer cell lines (MDA-MB- 231, B16F10, HepG2)⁹.

Additionally, another study focused on Myrrh (*Commiphora myrrha*), which contains 62% sesquiterpenes and is traditionally used by Arabians to treat skin conditions like wrinkles, chapped, and cracked skin. Eugenol exhibits antibacterial properties, thymol is commonly used in mouthwash for its antiseptic effects, and *chaulmoogra* oil is known for its therapeutic action in treating leprosy, among other uses. bioassay for the determination of elementary toxicity-Brine shrimp lethality test (BSLT) was used to determine the toxicity of the oil¹⁰

Nowadays, the brine shrimp (*Artemia salina*, also known as fairy shrimp or sea monkeys) lethality assay is widely used to assess the cytotoxic effects of bioactive chemicals. It is a preliminary toxicity screening of plant extracts, fungal toxins, heavy metals, cyanobacteria toxins, pesticides, cytotoxicity testing of dental material and nano structures. Subsequently animal model is recommended for its establishment. Additional laboratory equipment assays are yellow fever mosquito larvae lethality assay. Among these, the brine shrimp lethality test is the simplest, most cost-effective, and efficient method. The larvae (nauplii; singular nauplius), approximately 22 mm in length, are large enough to be observed without high magnification, yet small enough to be hatched in large quantities without requiring a significant amount of laboratory space. This lethality assay has been successively employed as a bioassay guide for active cytotoxic and anti tumor agents in 1982¹¹.

This test is a quick and thorough method for evaluating bioactive compounds, whether of natural or synthetic origin. It is also low-cost and easy to perform, as it does not require aseptic techniques. It easily utilizes a large number of organisms for statistical validation and requires no special equipment and relatively small amount of sample (2-20 mg or less) is necessary. Brine Shrimp Lethality Test (BSLT) is often used as an alternative to traditional animal studies for assessing the toxicity of substances. This method provides a cost-effective, ethical, and efficient means to evaluate the lethal effects of chemicals or natural extracts without the need for mammals or other higher animals.¹²

Nature of essential oil

Despite their rich and Complex structure composition, the use of essential oils is primarily confined to the cosmetics and perfumery industries. It is important to deepen our understanding of their chemical makeup and the biological properties of these extracts, along with their individual

components, to explore new and valuable applications in human health, agriculture, and the environment. Essential oils could serve as effective alternatives or supplements to synthetic chemicals in the industry, without causing the same side effects.¹³

These oils are complex mixtures of various bioactive chemical compounds, including terpenes, terpenoids, and phenylpropenes. They can be produced by more than 17,000 aromatic plant species commonly belonging to angiospermic families, such as Lamiaceae, Zingiberaceae, and Asteraceae¹⁴

Essential oils, also known as "essences" are volatile and odorous substances found in plants and are extracted by steam distillation, or by co-distillation with solvents. Essential oils are concentrated, complex substances found in the form of oily droplets within various parts of aromatic plants, such as flowers (Jasmine), leaves (Sage), fruits (Orange), seeds (Fennel), bark (Cinnamon), and roots (Angelica)¹⁵. Aromatic plant and their essential oils have been used since antiquity as condiments, spices, antimicrobial, insecticidal and agents to protect stored products. Natural additives derived from plants can include individual compounds, groups of compounds, or essential oils. Essential oils possess antiseptic properties and demonstrate antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, antiparasitic, and insecticidal effects. They have been shown to exert many biological activities, such as antimicrobial, analgesic, sedative, anti-inflammatory and spasmolytic.¹⁶

Essential oil is a natural secretion produced by secretory glands found in various parts of aromatic plants and trees, including the seed, root, wood, leaf, flower, and fruit. Only an essential oil obtained by distillation of a plant, botanically defined, in an alembic through steam under low pressure corresponds to the french association for standardization (AFNOR standard). The product obtained by applying mechanical pressure to citrus peels is referred to as non-essential oil.¹⁷

Essential oils are aromatic, volatile liquids composed of organic compounds extracted from plant materials, known for their strong and typically pleasant fragrance. The essential oils have been widely used as safe flavoring agents or preservatives in foods, in cosmetic or pharmaceutical products¹⁸. Essence is a natural substance secreted by aromatic plants. For citrus, essences are extracted by pressing the peel, commonly referred to as lemon oil or lemon essential oil. During the distillation process, the essence undergoes biochemical changes and transforms into essential oil. The essential oil represents the essence of the distilled plant. It consists of volatile molecules, and pure essential oil contains no natural fats. Essential oils are used in foods, medicines and cosmetics¹⁹.

Extraction of volatile oil

Several parts of various aromatic plants can be extracted and form essential oils which subsequently have many applications in cosmetics, pharmaceutical and food safety fields. The manufacturing method and technique used to extract essential oils are dependent on the characteristics and components required in the botanical extract. The main factor to ensure the quality of essential oils is the extraction method used, since inappropriate extraction procedures may cause the destruction and vary the action of phytochemicals present in aromatic oils. The resulting effects can be, for example, the loss of pharmacological constituents, stain effect, off flavor/ odour, and physical change of essential oils²⁰.

Extraction techniques can be categorized into two categories: classical methods and innovative

methods. The Conventional Extraction Methods are hydro distillation, steam distillation, hydro diffusion, solvent extraction. The innovative techniques are ultrasonic and microwave enhanced processes, has improved the efficiency of extraction process in terms time required for isolation of the essential oil and energy dissipation, as well as improvement in production yield, and high quality of essential oils²¹. However, the effectiveness of the extraction process and its safety are crucial priorities. As the limits for solvent residues are increasingly scrutinized, extracts obtained using supercritical fluids could play a key role in replacing toxic solvents²². One of the most important aspects of any extraction is likely the intimate contact between the substrate and the extraction method, as it can be a defining factor in determining the quality of the extract and ensuring the final product meets consumer expectations. However, extraction with supercritical fluids allows the extraction of the high quality products which are solvents-free. But, technological conditions for the use of the supercritical fluids expensive, which limits their use. Beside the essential oils, the supercritical CO₂ extracts contains various compounds²³.

Isolation and purification of volatile oil

The components in the extracts from the above methods are complex mixture and contains various type of natural products with different polarities. To obtain pure bioactive compound involves further separation and purification. Their separation remains a big challenge for the process of identification and characterization of pure bioactive natural product. Purification and isolation of natural products has undergone new development in recent years²⁴. A variety of separation techniques, including TLC, HPTLC, paper chromatography, column chromatography, gas chromatography, and HPLC, have been employed to isolate and purify many bioactive natural products. Column chromatography and thin-layer chromatography (TLC) are still mostly used due to their convenience, economy, and availability in various stationary phases. Besides that, non- chromatographic techniques uses such as immunoassay, which use monoclonal antibodies (MAbs), phytochemical screening assay. The pure compounds are then used for the determination of structure and biological activity.

Several of the commonly used separation techniques of the natural products are discussed below:

- Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)
- Column Chromatography (CC)
- Gas Chromatography (GC)
- High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)
- High Performance thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC)
- Optimum performance laminar chromatography (OPLC) ²

Structural determination

Determination of the structure of natural products uses data from a wide range of spectroscopic techniques such as UV-Visible, Infrared (IR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and Mass spectroscopy. The basic principle of spectroscopy is passing electromagnetic radiation through an organic compound that absorbs some of the radiation, but not all. A spectrum can be generated by measuring the absorption of electromagnetic radiation. The spectra are specific to certain bonds in a

compound. Depending on these spectra, The structure of the natural compound can be identified. Scientists mainly use spectra produced from either three or four regions Ultraviolet (UV), Visible, Infrared (IR), Radio frequency (FTIR), and electron beam for structural clarification²⁶.

Brine shrimp lethality assay

The cytotoxicity test was conducted on the brine shrimps, *Artemia salina*.

1. Material and equipment

- Rectangular glass jar
- Measuring cylinder (1000 mL)
- Table salt (27 g)
- Spatula
- Brine shrimp eggs (a few gram)
- Air pump
- Analytical balance
- Pasteur pipette
- Light source
- Microtip pipette
- Test tubes (12 × 100 mm)
- Magnifying glass
- Test sample of plant extract

2. Preparation of sample solution:

Stock solution was prepared by emulsifying 20 mg of the essential oils separately in 0.3ml of dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) and the volume was made up with 1.7ml of fresh sea water to equal 1000 ppm concentration. Next, a serial dilution was performed to obtain two additional concentrations of 100 ppm and 10 ppm.

3. Protocol for hatching brine shrimp

1. Measure 3 liters of water using measuring cylinder and pour into the rectangular jar
2. Weigh approximately 27 g of table salt using a balance, and then add it to the jar containing water.
3. Mix the water with a spatula
4. Place the tip of an airline from a air pump into the bottom of the jar maintaining proper aeration
5. Add approximately 15 g of brine shrimp eggs to the surface of the water in the jar and mix them in.
6. Turn on a light (60-100 Watt bulb) and place it a few inches above the jar.
7. Add about 15 g of brine shrimp eggs at the top water level of the jar and mix with the water
8. Switch on a light (60-100 Watt bulb) placed a few inches away from the jar
9. After 20-24 hours, the nauplii will hatch.
10. The hatched nauplii should be separated from the empty eggs. This can be done by turning

off the air and switching off the lamp. The empty eggs will float, while the brine shrimp will concentrate in the water column.

11. Using a Pasteur pipette, transfer 10 nauplii to a test tube.²⁷

Toxicity Testing

12. Expose the nauplii to different concentrations of the plant extract. After 24 hours, count the number of survivors and calculate the percentage of death.²⁸

Toxicity analysis of volatile oil from different medicinal plant by using brine shrimp lethality assay

1. *Moringa oleifera*

Moringa leaves (*Moringa oleifera*) are herbal plants that are often found among people, especially in tropical areas, and are widely spread in Indonesia Moringa leaves contain flavonoids, tannins, steroids, saponins, and alkaloids, which shows that they have antioxidant power²⁹

Several studies have shown that the compounds contained in *Moringa oleifera* L have potential as drugs and have bioactivity, including anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antibiotics, and, as well as antioxidants. The results of the study show that parts of Moringa contain compounds that function as antitumor, antipyretic, antiepileptic, antifertility, antihypertensive, and antidiabetic^{30,31}.

Isolation of Essential Oils from Moringa leaf by the Ethanol Maceration Method. Then find out the GC-MS results on Moringa leaves obtained fifteen (15) compound peaks. The GC-MS results of the volatile compounds identified were Iso-Valeric Acid, Methane sulphinic Acid Methyl Ester, 2-Pyrrolidinone, 2,3-Dihydro-Benzofuran, Benzene acetic Acid, Anthracene, 3-Buten-2-One, Nonadecane, 4 Hydroxy phenylacetamide, Cyclohexadecane, 2-Hexadecen-1-Ol, Octadecanoic Acid, 7-Isopropyl-4a-Methyloctahydro-2(1H)-Naphthalenone, Cyclooctene, Stigmasta-5,24(28)- Dien-3-Ol. *Artemia salina* Leach shrimp larvae were used to assess the toxicity of essential oil extracted from Moringa leaves. According to the findings of this study, the essential oil of Moringa leaves has an LC50 value of 178.58 ppm and is harmful to the larvae of the shrimp *Artemia salina* Leach³².

2. *Myristica fragrans* houtt., (NUTMEG)

Nutmeg (*Myristica fragrans* Houtt.), a medium-sized tree grown in tropical regions, is the source of two highly valued medicinal spices: nutmeg (the endosperm) and mace (the reddish aril), both of which possess a rich diversity of phytochemicals³³.

Recent reports on its antibacterial, antiviral, antidiabetic, antileukaemic effects and other biological activities suggest its enormous therapeutic potential. The nutmeg also showed a potent hepatoprotective activity against liver damage caused by certain chemicals. The protective activity was correlated with myristicin, a major constituent of nutmeg and recently it was found that myristicin induces cytotoxicity in human neuroblastoma SK-N-SH cells by an apoptotic mechanism³⁴.

Nutmeg is claimed to possess anti-cancer properties due to the presence of safrole derivatives, myristicin, β -sitosterol and methyl eugenol. The difference in the biological activity between the experimented and reported essential oil could be explained by the synergism, antagonism and additive effects³⁵.

The essential oil of *Myristica fragrans* (nutmeg) was extracted by steam distillation using

modified Clevenger's apparatus. The obtained essential oil was analysed for phytochemical properties and cytotoxicity. Phytochemical studies identified the presence of flavonoids, terpenoids, anthraquinones, cardiac glycosides, and steroids in the oil.

Brine shrimp bioassay performed with the plant oil, the present study shows concentrations (LC50) were determined to be $5434.78 \pm 23.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Potassium dichromate was used as a positive control, where the LC50 was determined to be $97.01 \pm 9.3 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Nutmeg essential oil showed non-toxicity according to Meyer et al.²⁵, who classified crude extracts and pure substances into toxic (LC50 value $< 1000 \mu\text{g/ml}$) and non-toxic (LC50 value $> 1000 \mu\text{g/ml}$). therefore the result shows LC50 of the essential oil was determined in the brine shrimp toxicity test to be $5434.78 \pm 23.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$, which is not cytotoxic (LC50 $> 1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$). nutmeg essential oil exhibited low toxicity³⁶.

3. *Ocimum gratissimum*

The nutritional importance of *Ocimum gratissimum* centres on its usefulness as a seasoning because of its aromatic flavour. *O. gratissimum* is an essential ingredient in the local Cuisine popularly known as 'pepper soup' and relished by many in South Western Nigeria³⁷.

In the southern part of the country, crude aqueous extract of *O. gratissimum* is commonly used in the treatment of epilepsy, high fever and diarrhoea. In the Savannah areas, decoctions of the leaves are used to treat mental illness. It is used by the Igbo community of south eastern Nigeria in the management of the baby's cord, to keep the wound surfaces sterile. It is also used in the treatment of fungal infections, fever, cold and catarrh. Inhabitants of the Brazilian tropical forest use a decoction of *O. gratissimum* to treat digestive disorders³⁸. In Kenya, it is a significant herbal remedy; the leaves are rubbed between the palms and inhaled to treat blocked nostrils. They are also used for abdominal pains, sore eyes, and ear infections, for coughs, barrenness, and fever, convulsions, and tooth gargle, regulation of menstruation and as a cure for prolapsed of the rectum. In India, the whole plant has been used for the treatment of sunstroke, headache, and influenza, as a diaphoretic, antipyretic and for its anti-inflammatory activity³⁹.

Hydro-distillation of the leaves and seeds of *O. gratissimum* gave light yellow and orange volatile oils respectively. The essential oil yields of the leaves and seeds were 0.97% and 0.83% respectively. Nine constituents representing 97.09% of total oil from the leaves were identified and Twenty-two compounds representing 98.41% of the total oil were identified from the seeds essential oil. The main constituents of the leaves essential oils were found to be γ -terpinene (52.86%), z-tert-butyl-4-hydroxy anisole (13.93%), caryophyllene (10.37%), and P-cymene (7.16%), thymol (3.65%), γ -selinene (3.45%) and caryophyllene oxide (2.68%). On the other hand, the major constituents of the seeds essential oil were α -pinene (48.19%), 3-tert Butyl-4- hydroxyl anisole (11.14%) and caryophyllene (10.71%). Other constituents were α - selinene (4.00%), caryophyllene oxide (3.45%), p-cymenene (3.86%) and thymol (3.29%). Six compounds were found to be common constituents of the leaves and the seeds essential oils of *O. gratissimum*. They were caryophyllene, caryophyllene oxide, p-cymenene, γ selinene, tert-butyl-4-hydroxy anisole and thymol.

Artemia salina nauplii were found to be highly susceptible to the essential oils of *O. gratissimum*. The cytotoxicity test was performed on the brine shrimp, *Artemia salina*, using the

method of modifications. At a concentration of 1000 ppm for all the extracts, the ten brine shrimp used in each triplicate died after 24 hours, resulting in 100% mortality of the nauplii. Mortality of 93-97% was recorded for 100ppm concentrations. The susceptibility of the nauplii at 10ppm ranges between 55-86% mortality. Finally the result shows the LC50 of the essential oil leaf and seed was determined in the brine shrimp toxicity test to be 3.6031 μ g/mL and 8.1588 μ g/mL. The essential oil showed less toxic activity.⁴⁰

4. *Ceiba pentandra* (Linn.,)

Ceiba pentandra (Linn.) Gaertn. (commonly known as the silk cotton tree) is a significant plant within the Bombacaceae family, renowned for its numerous medicinal and pharmacological properties. Almost all parts of the plant such as the leaves, stems, roots, gum, spines, flowers, heartwood, and seeds are used in traditional medicine to treat a variety of ailments, including diabetes, dysentery, insect bites, arthritis, mental disorders, constipation, fever, dizziness, peptic ulcers, leprosy, edema, diarrhea, and headaches, among others. Among the pharmacological activities reported in the literatures are anti-inflammatory, angiogenesis, anti-diarrheal, antihelmintic, antihypertensive, antimicrobial, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, hypoglycaemic, hypolipidemic, antiulcerogenic and cytotoxicity.⁴¹

Therefore, the current study was conducted to analyze the chemical profiles and brine shrimp toxicity of the volatile oils extracted from the stem bark and heartwood of *Ceiba pentandra*. A total of 28 compounds were identified in the stem bark oil equivalent to 98.8% of the whole oil. The volatile oil primarily consisted of terpenes, with sesquiterpene hydrocarbons accounting for 75.6%. The most abundant constituents were β -caryophyllene (28.7%), β -elemene (18.5%), α -muurolene (7.8%), caryophyllene oxide (4.8%), and α -humulene (4.2%). Both β -caryophyllene and caryophyllene oxide are commonly used as additives in food and cosmetics. In contrast, 22 components were identified in the heartwood oil, making up 76.8% of the total oil. The stem bark oil was largely non-terpenes (40.5%). The most abundant constituents were α -eudesmol (21.1%), 2-ethoxyacetate (11.3%) and nonanal (7.3%). A total of 28 and 22 constituents were identified in the stem bark and heartwood oils equivalent to 96.7% and 76.8% of the whole EOs respectively.

The essential oils extracted from both the stem bark and heartwood of *Ceiba pentandra* were colorless, with percentage yields of 0.14% w/w and 0.09% w/w, respectively. The stem bark and heartwood oils exhibited good brine shrimp lethality with LC50 of 25.9 and 89.8 μ g/mL, respectively. The chemical profiles and brine shrimps toxicity of these oils are been reported for the first time.⁴²

5. *Acalypha ornata*

Acalypha ornata Hochst is a shrub commonly found throughout tropical Africa. It is claimed to have several medicinal uses even though not much is known about its chemistry and pharmacology. Several species of the family, *A. indica*, *A. fruticosa*, *A. guatemalensis*, *A. wilkesiana*, *A. siamensis*, *A. communis*, *A. marginata* have however been widely investigated. They are found to contain condensed and hydrolysable tannins as well as flavonoid glycosides. Antimicrobial activities and anticancer potential of some *Acalypha* species have also been reported^{43,44}.

The aim of this research work is to determine the volatile oil constituent of the leaves of *Acalypha*

ornata which will be obtained by hydro distillation and analysed by Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC/GC-MS)

The yield of the 300 g hydrodistilled *A. ornata* leaves oil was 0.60% (w/w). The essential oil, colourless, with characteristic smell was analyzed by GC and GC/MS systems using a polar column, resulting in the identification of 89 constituents in the hydro distilled sample, representing 54.64% of the total essential oil. The Majority of the compounds are less than 1-2% of the total composition except the following compounds: isopulegyl acetate, valenche, viridiflorene, α - muurolene, 2-hexyne, 6-methyl- α -ionone, γ -elemene, (E)-2-methyl-4-undecene, ledol, cis-3- hexenyl benzoate, 2-methyl -1-octadecene, apiole, oplopamone and γ -eudesmol. Monoterpenes common in the essential oil of plants are found present though in trace amount in the essential oil of *A. ornata*.

The result of brine shrimp lethality test as analyzed by Finney probit computer programme showed that the oil from the leaves of *A.ornata* was toxic having an LC50 value of 111.6 mg/ml with lower and upper confidence limits of 26.38 μ g/ml and 239.45 μ g/ml respectively therefore it use at concentrations should be monitored. The high toxicity can also be beneficial in the therapy of some ailments involving cell or tumour growth. It has been found out that medicinally active natural products are most times toxic to *Artemia salina* nauplii ⁴⁵.

6.Thymus vulgaris

Certain essential oils (EOs) have been labeled as promising anticancer agents and are currently being investigated for their cytotoxic and antiproliferative activities in cancer cell lines or experimental animals ⁴⁶.

Various mechanisms have been reported for the cytotoxic effects of essential oils (EOs) or their individual constituents. These include induction of cell death by apoptosis and/or necrosis, antimutagenic, antiproliferative, antioxidant properties, cell cycle arrest, and loss of key organelle functions ⁴⁷. Research has shown that essential oils exhibit anticancer potential against various cancers, including those of the mouth, breast, lung, prostate, liver, colon, brain, and even leukemia. Studies suggest that specific components of essential oils enhance the cytotoxic activity of chemotherapy drugs such as docetaxel, paclitaxel, and 5-fluorouracil on different cell lines. This opens the possibility of reducing the dosage of these drugs while maintaining their effectiveness

Oxygenated monoterpenes and monoterpene hydrocarbons are the primary chemical components of *Thymus vulgaris* L. essential oil. The natural terpenoid thymol and its phenolic isomer, carvacrol, are the predominant compounds in this oil⁴⁸.

Non-clinical data indicate that thyme essential oil possesses potent antibacterial, antifungal, spasmolytic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. On the basis of a summary review of available data, it is evident that thymol may be a promising plant-derived cancer chemotherapeutic agent. *T. vulgaris* L. extracts are reported to possess anticancer potential, according to the several researches. These include significant free radical scavenging activity and proapoptotic effects in the human BC T47D cell line, inhibition of proliferation of colorectal HCT116 cancer cell line, and tumor inhibitory effects on human leukemia THP-1 cells. The capability of the *T. vulgaris* L. essential oil to significantly inhibit the growth of human oral cavity squamous cell carcinoma has been reported.

Evaluation of cytotoxic activity of thyme essential oil demonstrated antiproliferative and proapoptotic effects on the two independent human breast adenocarcinoma cell lines.^{49,50,51}

However, a further investigation is needed in order to estimate the anticancer potential of thyme essential oil. It has been proven that the brine shrimp lethality test (BSLT) has a good correlation with cytotoxic activity in some human solid tumors.⁵² Application of BSLT in cytotoxic assays has been described for several essential oils. Although the BSLT is able to identify strong anticancer activity of tested compound, its main limitation is its sensitivity to distinguish between strong to moderate and weak anti-cancer potentials. Therefore, the BSLT serves as a screening tool for potential cytotoxins, but a more precise assessment of anticancer activity requires testing on human cancer cells. This study focuses on evaluating the antiproliferative activity of chemically characterized *T. vulgaris* L. essential oil against breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7) cells, lung carcinoma (H460) cells, and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (MOLT-4) cells. Additionally, the cytotoxic concentration range and the cytotoxicity validation in cancer cell lines, along with the brine shrimp lethality of thyme essential oil, were tested and analyzed⁵³.

The essential oil of *T. vulgaris* L., isolated by hydro-distillation, was yellowish in color, clear, with an aromatic thymol odor, and yielded 1.5% (v/w) on a dry weight basis. Qualitative and quantitative analyses were performed using gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC-MS). A total of 32 components were identified in the thyme essential oil. The oil was predominantly composed of monoterpene hydrocarbons (47.6%) and oxygenated monoterpenes (49.2%), which were present in nearly equal proportions and together made up approximately 97% of the oil's composition. In contrast, aliphatic compounds (1.30%), sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (0.4%), and oxygenated sesquiterpenes (0.5%) were present in smaller amounts. The major components in the monoterpene hydrocarbon fraction were p-cymene (30.0%) and γ -terpinene (9.0%). The most significant components in the oxygenated monoterpene fraction were thymol (36.7%) and carvacrol (3.6%).

The LC50 values obtained from the brine shrimp lethality bioassay for *T. vulgaris* L. essential oil and thymol (used as a positive control) were 60.38 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 16.67 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively⁵⁴

Conclusion:

In conclusion, essential oils from medicinal plants offer significant therapeutic potential due to their bioactive compounds with antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties. The Brine Shrimp Lethality Test (BSLT) is a simple and effective method for evaluating their cytotoxicity. This study showed diverse toxicity levels among various oils: *Moringa oleifera* showed moderate toxicity, *Myristica fragrans* was minimally toxic, and *Ocimum gratissimum* exhibited high toxicity. Oils from *Ceiba pentandra*, *Acalypha ornata*, and *Thymus vulgaris* demonstrated varying degrees of cytotoxicity, indicating potential applications in disease treatment. While promising, further research including human cell line studies is needed to fully assess their safety and efficacy.

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References:

1. Rubiolo, P., Liberto, E., Matteodo, M., Sgorbini, B., Mondello, L., Zellner, B. A., Costa, R., & Bicchi, C. (2008). Quantitative analysis of essential oils: A complex task. *Flavour and Fragrance Journal*, 23, 382–391. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ffj.1875>
2. Egza, T. F. (2020). A review on extraction, isolation, characterization and some biological activities of essential oils from various plants. *Global Scientific Journal*, 8(1). ISSN 2320-9186.
3. Pandey, A. K., Kumar, P., Singh, P., Tripathi, N. N., & Bajpai, V. K. (2017). Essential oils: Sources of antimicrobials and food preservatives. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 16, 2161. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.02161>
4. Chaieb, K., Hajlaoui, H., Zmantar, T., Kahla, N. A. B., Rouabhia, M., Mahdouani, K., & Bakhrouf, A. (2007). The chemical composition and biological activity of clove essential oil, *Eugenia caryophyllata* (Syzygium aromaticum L. Myrtaceae): A short review. *Phytotherapy Research*, 21, 501–506. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.2124>
5. Wińska, K., Mączka, W., Lyczko, J., Grabarczyk, M., Czubaszek, A., & Szumny, A. (2019). Essential oils as antimicrobial agents—Myth or real alternative? *Molecules*, 24(11), 2130. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24112130>
6. Bowles, E. J. (2004). *The chemistry of aromatherapeutic oils* (3rd ed.). Crows Nest, NSW: Allen & Unwin Academic.
7. Chatterjee, S., Niaz, Z., Gautam, S., Adhikari, S., Variyar, P. S., & Sharma, A. (2007). Antioxidant activity of some phenolic constituents from green pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.) and fresh nutmeg mace (*Myristica fragrans*). *Food Chemistry*, 101, 515–523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.02.044>
8. Gautam, N., Mantha, A. K., & Mittal, S. (2014). Essential oils and their constituents as anticancer agents: A mechanism view. *BioMed Research International*, Article ID 154106. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/154106>
9. Michael, A. S., Thompson, C. G., & Abramowitz, M. (1956). *Artemia salina* as a test organism for bioassay. *Science*, 123(3194), 464. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.123.3194.464>
10. Sarah, Q. S., Anny, F. C., & Misbahuddin, M. (2017). Brine shrimp lethality assay. *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology*, 12, 186–189. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjp.v12i2.31965>
11. Kibiti, C., & Afolayan, A. (2016). Antifungal activity and brine shrimp toxicity assessment of *Bulbine abyssinica* used in folk medicine in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology*, 11, 469–477. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjp.v11i2.26218>
12. Zeng, Q. H., Zhao, J. B., Wang, J. J., Zhang, X. W., & Jiang, J. G. (2016). Extraction of essential oils using supercritical fluid. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 68, 595–603.
13. Si Saidi, B. O., Haddadi-Guemgha, H., Boulekbache-Makhlouf, L., Rigou, P., Remini, H., Adjaoud, A., Khoudja, K., & Madani, K. (2016). Phenolic profile and antioxidant activity of some essential oils. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 89, 167–175.
14. Arranz, E., Jaime, L., López de las Hazas, M. C., Reglero, G., & Santoyo, S. (2015). Supercritical fluid extraction of bioactives. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 67, 121–129.

15. Egza, T. F. (n.d.). A review on extraction, isolation, characterization and some biological activities of essential oils from various plants. Department of Chemistry, College of Natural Sciences, Arba Minch University, Ethiopia. Email: tsefik05@gmail.com
16. Tongnuanchan, P., & Benjakul, S. (2014). Essential oils: Extraction, bioactivities, and their uses for food preservation. *Journal of Food Science*, 79(7), R1231–R1249. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.12492>
17. El Asbahani, A., Miladi, K., Badri, W., Sala, M., Addi, E. H. A., Casabianca, H., El Mousadik, A., Hartmann, D., Jilale, A., Renaud, F. N. R., & Elaissari, A. (2015). Essential oils: From extraction to encapsulation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 483, 220–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2014.12.069>
18. Mejri, J., Aydi, A., Abderrabba, M., & Mejri, M. (2018). Emerging extraction processes of essential oils: A review. *Asian Journal of Green Chemistry*, 2, 246–267. <https://doi.org/10.22034/ajgc.2018.53660>
19. Rezzoug, S. A., Boutekedjiret, C., & Allaf, K. (2005). Extraction of essential oils using innovative techniques. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 71, 9–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2004.10.036>
20. Reverchon, E. (1997). Supercritical fluid extraction and fractionation of essential oils and related products. *Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, 10(1), 1–37. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0896-8446\(97\)00027-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0896-8446(97)00027-2)
21. Oszagyan, M., Simandi, B., Sawinsky, J., Kery, A., Lemberkovics, E., & Fekete, J. (1996). Supercritical fluid extraction of essential oils. *Flavour and Fragrance Journal*, 11, 157–165. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1026\(199605\)11:3<157::AID-FFJ586>3.0.CO;2-F](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1026(199605)11:3<157::AID-FFJ586>3.0.CO;2-F)
22. Zibetti, A. W., Aydi, A., Livia, M. A., Bolzan, A., & Barth, D. (2013). Extraction of essential oils with supercritical fluids. *Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, 83, 133–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2013.08.020>
23. Sasidharan, S., Chen, D., Saravanan, K. M., Sundram, K. M., & Latha, L. Y. (2010). Extraction, isolation and characterization of bioactive compounds from plant extracts. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 8(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajtcam.v8i1.60483>
24. Zhang, W. Q., Lin, G. L., & Ye, C. W. (2018). Techniques for extraction and isolation of natural products: A comprehensive review. *Chinese Medicine*, 13(20), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13020-018-0177-x>
25. Popova, I. E., Hall, C., & Kubátová, A. (2008). Determination of lignans in flaxseed using liquid chromatography with time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1216(2), 217–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2008.11.063>
26. Sarah, Q. S., Chowdhury, F. A., & Misbahuddin, M. (2017). Brine shrimp lethality assay. *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology*, 12(2), 186–189. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjp.v12i2.32796> [Bangladesh Journals Online+3CABI Digital Library+3Directory of Open Access Journals+3](https://www.banglajol.info/index.php/BJP)

27. Oberlies, N. H., Rogers, L. L., Martin, J. M., & McLaughlin, J. L. (1998). Cytotoxic and insecticidal constituents of the unripe fruit of *Persea americana*. *Journal of Natural Products*, 61(6), 781–785. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np9800304PMC+1PubMed+1>
28. Amin, M. A., Anwar, H., & Haeruddin. (2018). Pengaruh bauran pemasaran jasa terhadap minat kembali pasien non asuransi di poli rawat jalan Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Daya Kota Makassar. *Jurnal Mitrasehat*, 8(2), 479–488. <https://doi.org/10.51171/jms.v8i2.207ResearchGate+2journal.stikmks.ac.id+2Jurnal Pascasarjana UMI+2>
29. Styowati, A., Sumarni, S., & Fatmsari, D. (2023). Nanopartikel daun kelor (*Moringa oleifera* Lamk.) terhadap perubahan kadar kalsium darah dan tekanan darah pada wanita usia subur hipertensi. *Jurnal Keperawatan Silampari*, 6(2), 1256–1262. <https://doi.org/10.31539/jks.v6i2.5426>
30. Allisandra, M. D. R. (2023). Molecular docking senyawa turunan flavonoid dengan protein 3KC0 dan uji aktivitas antidiabetes ekstrak daun kelor pada mencit jantan (*Mus musculus*) [Undergraduate thesis, Universitas Lampung]. http://digilib.unila.ac.id/72374/Digital_Library Unila+1Digital_Library Unila+1
31. Setianingsih, N. L. P. P., Sudiarta, I. W., Andriani, A. A. S. P. R., Jiwantara, G. N. O., Djelantik, S. A. M. A. P., & Darmawan, K. D. R. (2023). Toxicity test of moringa (*Moringa oleifera* Lam) essential oil with the brine shrimp lethality test (BSLT) method. *International Journal of Scientific Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(6), 627–640. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijsmr.v1i6.5255ResearchGate>
32. Lee, B. K., Kim, J. H., Jung, J. W., Choi, J. W., Han, E. S., Lee, S. H., Ko, K. H., & Ryu, J. H. (2005). Myristicin-induced neurotoxicity in human neuroblastoma SK-N-SH cells. *Toxicology Letters*, 157(1), 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2005.03.002>
33. Ju, Y. H., Clausen, L. M., Allred, K. F., Almada, A. L., & Helferich, W. G. (2004). β -Sitosterol, β -sitosterol glucoside, and a mixture of β -sitosterol and β -sitosterol glucoside modulate the growth of estrogen-responsive breast cancer cells in vitro and in ovariectomized athymic mice. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 134(5), 1145–1151. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/134.5.1145>
34. Pisano, M., Pagnan, G., Loi, M., Mura, M. E., Tilocca, M. G., Palmieri, G., Fabbri, D., Dettori, M. A., Delogu, G., Ponzoni, M., & Rozzo, C. (2007). Antiproliferative and proapoptotic activity of eugenol-related biphenyls on malignant melanoma cells. *Anticancer Research*, 27(6B), 3603–3610.
35. Piaru, S. P., Mahmud, R., & Ismail, S. (2012). Studies on the phytochemical properties and brine shrimp toxicity of essential oil extracted from *Myristica fragrans* Houtt. (Nutmeg). *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 2(2), S611–S614. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2221-1691\(12\)60299-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2221-1691(12)60299-3)
36. Effraim, K. D., Jacks, T. W., & Sodipo, O. A. (2003). Histopathological studies on the toxicity of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves extract on some organs of rabbit. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*, 6(1), 21–25.

37. Ijeh, I. I., Omodamiro, O. D., & Nwanna, I. J. (2005). Antimicrobial effects of aqueous and ethanolic fractions of two spices, *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Xylopiya aethiopica*. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 4(9), 953–956.
38. Tania, U., Nakamura, R. R., & Mendonça, F. (2006). Antileishmanial activity of eugenol-rich essential oil from *Ocimum gratissimum*. *Parasitology International*, 55(2), 99–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parint.2005.11.001>
39. Owokotomo, I. A., Ekundayo, O., & Dina, O. (2012). *Ocimum gratissimum*: The brine shrimps lethality of a new chemotype grown in South Western Nigeria. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research*, 12(3), 1–7.
40. Bhushan, G., Kavimani, S., & Rajkapor, B. (2011). Antiulcer activity of methanolic extract of *Ceiba pentandra* Linn Gaertn on rats. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*, 4(11), 4132–4134.
41. Abouelela, M. E., Orabi, M. A. A., Abdelhamid, R. A., Abdelka, M. S. A., & Darwish, F. M. M. (2018). Chemical and cytotoxic investigation of non-polar extract of *Ceiba pentandra* (L.) Gaertn.: A study supported by computer-based screening. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 8(7), 57–64. <https://doi.org/10.7324/JAPS.2018.8710>
42. Alade, A. T., Satyal, P., Aboaba, S. O., & Setzer, W. N. (2021). Chemical profiles and brine shrimp toxicity of volatile oils hydrodistilled from stem bark and heartwood of *Ceiba pentandra* Linn. *American Journal of Essential Oils and Natural Products*, 9(3), 22–26.
43. Gutierrez, L., Singh, M. P., Maiese, W. M., & Timmermann, B. N. (2002). New antimicrobial cycloartane triterpenes from *Acalypha communis*. *Journal of Natural Products*, 65(6), 872–875. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np0105384>
44. Reed, J. D. (1995). Nutritional toxicology of tannins and related polyphenols in forage legumes. *Journal of Animal Science*, 73(5), 1516–1528. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1995.7351516x>
45. Sabina, K. C., & Claudie, M. H. (2005). Ethnomedicinal and bioactive properties of plants ingested by wild chimpanzees in Uganda. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 101(1–3), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2005.03.021>
46. Onocha, P. A., Oloyede, G. K., & Olasunkanmi, G. S. (2012). Chemical composition, brine shrimp toxicity and free-radical scavenging activity of leaf essential oil of *Acalypha ornata* (Hochst). *International Journal of Essential Oil Therapeutics*, 6(1), 1–5.
47. Edris, A. E. (2007). Pharmaceutical and therapeutic potentials of essential oils and their individual volatile constituents: A review. *Phytotherapy Research*, 21(4), 308–323. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.2072>
48. Gautam, N., Mantha, A. K., & Mittal, S. (2014). Essential oils and their constituents as anticancer agents: A mechanistic view. *BioMed Research International*, 2014, 154106. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/154106>
49. Carnesecchi, S., et al. (2001). Geraniol, a component of plant essential oils, inhibits growth and polyamine biosynthesis in human colon cancer cells. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 298(1), 197–200.
50. Heidari, Z., Salehzadeh, A., Shandiz, S. A., & Tajdoost, S. (2018). Anti-cancer and anti-oxidant

- properties of ethanolic leaf extract of *Thymus vulgaris* and its bio-functionalized silver nanoparticles. *3 Biotech*, 8, 177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-018-1211-8>
51. Al-Menhali, A., et al. (2015). *Thymus vulgaris* (thyme) inhibits proliferation, adhesion, migration, and invasion of human colorectal cancer cells. *Journal of Medicinal Food*, 18(1), 54–59. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jmf.2014.0037>
 52. Ayesh, B. M., Abed, A. A., & Doaa, M. F. (2014). In vitro inhibition of human leukemia THP-1 cells by *Origanum syriacum* L. and *Thymus vulgaris* L. extracts. *BMC Research Notes*, 7, 612. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1756-0500-7-612>
 53. McLaughlin, J. L., Rogers, L. L., & Anderson, J. E. (1998). The use of biological assays to evaluate botanicals. *Drug Information Journal*, 32(2), 513–524. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009286159803200226>
 54. Colegate, S. M., & Molyneux, R. J. (2007). *Bioactive natural products: Detection, isolation, and structural determination* (pp. 18–20). CRC Press.
 55. Niksic, H., Becic, F., Koric, E., Gusic, I., Omeragic, E., Muratovic, S., Miladinovic, B., & Duric, K. (2021). Cytotoxicity screening of *Thymus vulgaris* L. essential oil in brine shrimp nauplii and cancer cell lines. *Scientific Reports*, 11, 13178. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-92679-x>